

CyberNEMO
End-to-end Cybersecurity to NEMO meta-OS

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Key Facts

Duration: October 2024 – September 2027

EU Contribution: € 5.999.747,50

Programme: Horizon Europe Programme

The Consortium

Coordinator: SYNELIXIS LYSEIS PLIROFORIKIS AUTOMATISMOU & TILEPIKOINONION ANONIMI ETAIRIA (Greece)

Partners: A large, multidisciplinary consortium of 23 participants (plus 1 associated partner) from 11 European countries, bringing together industry leaders, research institutions, SMEs, and critical infrastructure operators.

The Challenge

The Horizon project NEMO (Next Generation Meta OS) builds an IoT-Edge-Cloud continuum in the form of an open-source, flexible meta-Operating System. However, this distributed continuum introduces significant cybersecurity and trust challenges that must be addressed end-to-end. CyberNEMO's primary objective is to build on top of NEMO to add end-to-end cybersecurity and trust across the IoT-Edge-Cloud-Data Computing Continuum. The project aims to establish a paradigm shift to support resilience, risk preparedness, awareness, detection, and mitigation within Critical Infrastructure deployments and across supply chains.

The Mission

The project's mission is to achieve technology maturity and massive adoption by leveraging existing "by-design, by-innovation, and by-collaboration" zero-trust cybersecurity and privacy protection systems, while introducing novel concepts, methods, and tools to go beyond today's state of the art. Its core approach delivers end-to-end and full-stack protection through five integrated components:

1. Low-level Zero-Trust Network Access (ZTNA) layer – Securing network connectivity.
2. Human-AI Explainable Situation Perception, Comprehension & Protection (SPCP) framework – Making AI-driven security decisions understandable.
3. Collaborative micro-services Auditing, Certification & Accreditation – Ensuring trust in distributed services.
4. Pan-European Knowledge Sharing, risk Assessment, threat Analysis & incidents Mitigation (SAAM) collaborative platform – Enabling cross-border intelligence sharing.
5. Deployment via the Eclipse Foundation ecosystem – Ensuring sustainability and adoption through Europe's de-facto open source foundation

The Impact

CyberNEMO Cybersecurity Framework

- End-to-End Zero-Trust Protection: Full-stack security from network access to human-AI decision support.
- SAAM Collaborative Platform: A pan-European platform for knowledge sharing, risk assessment, threat analysis, and incident mitigation.
- Auditing & Certification Tools: Collaborative micro-services for continuous compliance and accreditation.

Real-World Validation (6 Pilots)

- OneLab Integration – Foundational testing environment.
- Critical Infrastructures – Energy and Water
- Critical Infrastructures – Healthcare
- Media Distribution – Securing content supply chains.
- Smart Agriculture and Supply Chain – Enhancing resilience in food systems.
- Cross-domain & Cross-border Federation – Demonstrating interoperability across sectors and national boundaries.

Sustainability & Uptake

- Eclipse Foundation Hosting: Ensuring long-term open-source sustainability and European governance.
- Paradigm-Shift in Critical Infrastructure Protection: Establishing new standards for resilience, risk preparedness, and incident response.